

Title:

Solving the Coral Species Delimitation Conundrum

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Lines of evidence	Data	Analyses	Main outputs	Results summary	
Morphology	Morphometrical	Quantitative continuous characters with normal distribution and homogeneity of variance	Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) and multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA)	<p>Ward clustering dendrogram</p> <p>Scatterplot of discriminant functions and test for significant median differences</p> <p>Scatterplot of factor analysis using all variables</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delineation of three morphospecies • Identification of informative characters for species delimitation.
	Descriptive	Qualitative and categorized quantitative characters	Factor analysis of mixed data (FAMD) Hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA)		
Breeding trials	Reproductive compatibility	Fertilization success (FS%) calculated from the proportion of embryos (Em) compared to the number of embryos (Em) plus the remaining unfertilized eggs (Ue) 10 h after experiments were performed: $FS\% = \left[\frac{Em}{Em + Ue} \right] \times 100$	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test of mean fertilization success	<p>Box plots and tests for significant differences in mean fertilization success (%) between and within morphospecies compared to controls</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of three reproductively isolated groups congruent with morphospecies delineation
Molecular approaches	Screening of available markers	PCR-amplified and Sanger-sequenced markers: • mitochondrial AcroCR • PMCA • FZD	Model-based genetic clustering, allele sharing-based approach, distance-based approach and phylogenetic analyses	<p>Genetic clustering bar plots, haplowebs, pairwise genetic distance histograms and gene trees.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available markers do not provide enough resolution at species level
	Screening of target-enriched loci	Target enrichment using the scleractinian subset of the hexacorall v2 bait set. 2,060 conserved loci were captured and extracted into FASTA: 1,026 exons and 1,034 UCES. Allele phasing was then performed using two different pipelines: Laninsky and PHYLUCE	Laninsky SNPs data used for genetic clustering (1,889 loci) and estimation of a preliminary species tree using SNAPP (210 loci) PHYLUCE data (80 loci) used for the resolved extended species tree, species delimitation using SODA and allele sharing-based approaches	<p>Genetic clustering bar plots and consensus species tree obtained from maximum clade credibility trees.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of genetic clusters and estimation of the most likely species tree according to this data set
	Species delimitation using target-enrichment derived markers	PCR-amplified and Sanger-sequenced target-enrichment derived markers: • TDH • DOPR • ASNA	Model-based genetic clustering (Structure), discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) and different species delimitation approaches: distance-based, allele sharing-based, tree-based, and coalescence-based methods	<p>Resolved extended species tree, haplowebs and conspecificity matrix</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of loci with species-level resolution • Species delimitation using target-capture data
			<p>Model-based genetic clustering bar plot, discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) scatterplot, distribution of pairwise genetic distances, gene trees (individual and resolved extended species tree, haplowebs and conspecificity matrix, Bayes factor delimitation (BDF) and Bayesian species delimitation (BPP)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of target-enrichment derived markers for Sanger sequencing • Identification of genetic clusters • Delineation of species boundaries • Molecular species congruent with morphology and breeding trials 	

FIGURE S1. Multiple lines of evidence used to delineate species boundaries in the tabular *Acropora* from Sesoko Island (Okinawa, Japan). A summarized workflow of the lines of evidence used in this study is presented. The data used, the analyses, the main outputs and a brief summary of the results are shown.

MANOVA morphospecies Pillai's trace = 1.08, Df= 2, F (6, 140) = 27.45, $P < 2.20E-16$

FIGURE S2. Multivariate analyses of morphological characters. a) Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) of continuous variables exhibiting 81.08% accuracy in discriminating between morphospecies ($n=74$): B_width ($r = 0.49$, $P < 0.001$), B_height ($r = 0.51$, $P < 0.001$) and $B_distclosestbranch$ ($r = 0.19$, $P < 0.001$). The result of a one-way MANOVA test for these variables is also displayed. Additionally, statistically significant differences between species were found when using post-hoc univariate ANOVA tests for each dependent variable ($n=74$, $P < 0.001$ for each, see details in Dataset S1). b) Individual contribution (%) of each character to the mapping dimensions 1 (left) and 2 (right) of the FAMD. Each variable code corresponds to those described in Tables S1 and S2. The dashed lines indicate the average contribution value (%) for each dimension.

FIGURE S3. Preliminary screening of PMCA and FZD markers. a) Evanno ΔK plot suggesting the most likely K value (dashed line) for model-based genetic clustering. b) STRUCTURE plot obtained by assigning the probability of individual membership with $K=2$. b) Allele sharing-based haplowebs with shades corresponding to the groups delineated by morphology and breeding trials. c) Histograms of pairwise comparison of genetic distances within and between morphospecies. d) Ultrafast bootstrap trees for each phased marker with bootstrap support (BS) of 85-94% indicated by grey and BS $\geq 95\%$ by white circles at the corresponding nodes. Alleles for each individual are differentiated by the suffixes “_a” and “_b”.

FIGURE S4. Phylogenetic trees and genetic distance histograms for each marker derived from target-capture sequencing. Ultrafast bootstrap trees and pairwise genetic distances comparison within and between morphospecies for markers defined from target-capture sequencing: a) TDH, b) DOPR and c) ASNA. In the trees, nodes with less than 85% of support were collapsed whereas bootstrap support (BS) of 85 to 94% is indicated by grey and 95% by white circles at the corresponding nodes. Alleles of each individual are differentiated by the suffixes “_a” and “_b”.

FIGURE S5. Concatenated gene and species trees for the three target enrichment-derived markers. Phylogenetic trees of three target capture derived loci (TDH, DOPR and ASNA) shaded according to the primary species hypotheses (PSHs) regarding to morphospecies. a) Ultrafast bootstrap tree for the concatenated IUPAC consensus sequences of the three markers. Nodes with less than 85% of bootstrap support (BS) were collapsed. b) SNAPP cloudogram using SNP information extracted from the target enrichment defined markers, where each individual was allowed to be a terminal tip (i.e. without constraining individuals into species). c) ASTRAL extended species trees obtained by mapping alleles to individuals, where both morphospecies were monophyletically constrained (inset) and left unconstrained (main tree, resolved extended species trees). Nodes with less than 10% of local posterior probability (LPP) were collapsed.

TABLE S1. Qualitative (QL) and quantitative (QN) characters used for morphological taxonomic assessment.

Type	No.	Code	Character	(Coding) States / description
	1	Color	Colony color in the field	(1) yellow-brown; (2) darker-brown; (3) orange-brown
	2	Bthickness	Relative contribution of corallites to B thickness	(1) axial-dominated; (2) 50/50; (3) radial-dominated
	3	Btaper	Branch taper	(1) tapering; (2) terete
	4	Bradcrowding	Radial crowding (density) along the B	(1) radials do not touch; (2) some radials touch; (3) radials touching
	5	ACshape	Axial corallite dominant shape	(1) tubular; (2) conical; (3) barrel
	6	ACprimaryseprelradius	Relation of AC primary septum to R	(1) <1/4; (2) 1/4 to 3/4; (3) >3/4 R
	7	ACprominentdirectives	Number AC prominent directives	(0) 0; (1) 1; (2) 2
QL	8	RCshapedominant	RC dominant shape	(1) rounded lip; (2) flaring lip; (3) straight lip
	9	RCsizes	RC sizes	(1) one size; (2) two sizes; (3) mixed; (4) increasing down branch
	10	RCprimaryseprelradius	Relation of RC primary septum to R	(1) <1/4; (2) 1/4 to 3/4; (3) >3/4 R
	11	RCprominentdirectives	Number of RC prominent directives	(0) 0; (1) 1; (2) 2
	12	RCanglebranch	Approximate angle of the RC to the B	(1) 0-30°; (2) 30-60°; (3) 60-90°; (4) 90°
	13	CRtype	Coenosteum type on RC	(1) costate; (2) reticulate; (3) spinous
	14	CRspines	Coenosteum spines on RC	(0) none; (1) simple; (2) forked; (3) elaborate
	15	Ctype	Coenosteum type between RC	(1) costate; (2) reticulate; (3) spinous
	16	Cspines	Coenosteum spines between RC	(0) none; (1) simple; (2) forked; (3) elaborate

	17	B_width	Branch width	Diameter at the base of the B
	18	B_height	Branch height	Distance from tip to base of the B
	19	B_distclosestbranch	Distance to the closest branch	Distance from outer wall of AC to AC outer wall in the nearest B
	20	AC_calyxmaxdiam	Maximum diameter of axial calyx	Maximum distance between inner walls of the AC
	21	AC_maxdiam	Maximum diameter of axial corallite	Maximum distance between outer walls of the AC
QN	22	AC_wallthickness	Axial wall thickness	Difference between maximum diameters of the AC and calyx divided by two $(21-20)/2$
	23	Ncorallitesbranchdiam	Number of corallites per B	RC per branch diameter at point where B stops tapering
	24	RC_calyxdiamwidestarea	Radial calyx diameter in the widest area	Maximum distance between inner walls of the RC
	25	RC_outerdiamwidestarea	RC diameter in the widest area	Maximum distance between outer walls of the RC
	26	RC_wallthicknesswidestarea	RC wall thickness in the widest area	Wall width at the widest area of the RC
	27	RC_wallthicknesstip	RC wall thickness at the outer tip	Wall width at the outer tip of the RC

Color (No. 1) was assessed from photographs taken from each coral colony. Descriptive characters (2 – 16) were recorded from overall observation of skeletal fragments. Morphometric characters (17 – 19) were measured directly from the branches using Vernier callipers. Corallite features (20 – 27) were obtained using a stereo microscope and an ocular graticule (except for 23 that was counted from above). Character code: branch (B), axial corallite (AC), radial corallite (RC), radius (R).

TABLE S2. Transformation of quantitative morphometric variables.

Type	Code	N (P)	H (P)	Transformation
	B_width	0.0952	0.2637	N/A
QN	B_height	0.1766	0.1111	N/A
	B_distclosestbranch	0.0755	0.9618	N/A
CT	AC_calyxmaxdiam	<0.001	0.5962	Discretization: 3 L, B=[0.60, 0.78, 0.85, 1.04]
	AC_maxdiam	0.0052	0.5484	Discretization: 4 L, B=[1.34, 1.5, 1.68, 1.85, 2.01]
	AC_wallthickness	0.0002	0.2338	Discretization: 3 L, B=[0.15, 0.20, 0.23, 0.28]
	Ncorallitesbranchdiam	0.0011	0.0230	Discretization: 3 L, B=[5, 7, 9, 12]
	RC_calyxdiamwidestarea	<0.001	0.0214	Discretization: 3 L, B=[0.60, 0.70, 0.85, 1.04]
	RC_outerdiamewidestarea	0.0023	0.2130	Discretization: 3 L, B=[1.04, 1.25, 1.50, 1.79]
	RC_wallthicknesswidestarea	<0.001	0.5247	Discretization: 3 L, B=[0.11, 0.14, 0.18, 0.22]
	RC_wallthicknesstip	<0.001	0.0079	Discretization: 3 L, B=[0.22, 0.28, 0.35, 0.45]

A Shapiro-Wilk test for normality (N) and a Levene test for homogeneity of variances (H) was performed for each quantitative variable with a significance level (α) of 0.05. Quantitative variables that exhibited normal distribution and homoscedasticity ($P > \alpha$) were analyzed as continuous numeric variables (QN). The variables that did not conform to these assumptions (even after applying the optimal transformation using the bestNormalize R package v1.5.0) were discretized into categorical variables according to their distribution (arules R package v1.6-5), and analyzed along with the qualitative characters (CT). Number of levels (L) and breaks (B) are shown for each of those variables.

TABLE S3. Summary of techniques, loci and methods used in the different stages of the molecular analyses performed in this study.

Stage	Molecular technique	No. loci/markers [n= samples]	Pre-processing		Downstream analyses
Preliminary screening of available molecular markers	PCR-based amplification followed by Sanger sequencing	Three genetic markers (AcroCR, PMCA, FZD) [n= 36]	Chromatograms edition, sequence alignment and phasing		Genetic clustering, genetic distances and gene trees
Screening of target-enriched loci	Target enrichment and high-throughput sequencing of conserved elements (exons and UCEs) captured using the hexacoral-v2 bait set	2060 loci (1026 exons, 1034 UCEs) [n= 9]	Reads de-multiplexing and trimming, contigs assembly and probe matching	Phasing Laninsky pipeline Phasing PHYLUCE pipeline	Genetic clustering (1889 loci), SNAPP species tree (210 loci) Allele sharing-based approaches and extended species trees (79 loci)
Implementation of target-enrichment derived markers in molecular species delimitation	PCR-based amplification followed by Sanger sequencing	Three genetic markers (TDH, DOPR, ASNA) [n= 36]	Chromatograms edition, sequence alignment and phasing		Genetic clustering, genetic distances, gene trees, species trees, coalescent and allele sharing-based approaches

Detailed information about the techniques, the number of loci, the number of individual samples, and the general pre-processing steps and downstream analyses used at each stage of the molecular approaches used in this study.

TABLE S4. Samples included in the target enrichment sequencing.

Sample ID / Target enrichment ID	SRA accession ID	#C	Mean cov	# Loci (total) UCE / exon	Mean length (bp) UCE / exon
18Oki21 / Acropora_CFhyacinthus1C282	SAMN16242367	17611	22.5	1278 675 / 603	1019.7 / 1091.3
18Oki22 / Acropora_CFhyacinthus1C283	SAMN16242368	14902	28.8	1322 680 / 642	1085.9 / 1119.5
18Oki23 / Acropora_CFhyacinthus1C284	SAMN16242369	9907	22.8	1419 717 / 702	895.9 / 949.2
18Oki26 / Acropora_CFcynthia5C285	SAMN16242370	6718	11.3	1686 873 / 813	602.4 / 599.8
18Oki27 / Acropora_CFcynthia5C286	SAMN16242371	8530	21.3	1533 792 / 741	812.1 / 838.6
18Oki29 / Acropora_CFcynthia5C287	SAMN16242372	13314	19.6	1442 731 / 711	1001.4 / 1057.3
18Oki32 / Acropora_CFbifurcataC288	SAMN16242373	23124	38.8	1400 698 / 702	1131.2 / 1183.7
18Oki33 / Acropora_CFbifurcataC289	SAMN16242374	11723	16.2	1465 742 / 723	838.0 / 847.4
18Oki34 / Acropora_CFbifurcataC290	SAMN16242375	15105	23.2	1301 676 / 625	1068.9 / 1132.0

Summary of pre-processing statistics of the contigs assembled for the subset of tabular *Acropora* samples. For these samples, target enrichment sequencing was performed using a re-designed set of baits for Hexacorallia that included loci flanking both UCEs and exons (Cowman et al. 2020). Using this target capture approach, 2,060 loci (1,026 exons and 1,034 UCEs) were recovered for the nine samples. Sequence Read Archive (SRA) accession numbers for the raw data are also shown and are gathered under the Bioproject PRJNA665126. Number of contigs (#C), Mean coverage (Mean cov).

TABLE S5. Primers and conditions for PCR-based amplification and Sanger sequencing.

Loci (GenBank IDs)	PCR primers (5' - 3')	PCR conditions	Sequencing primers (5' - 3')	Product length (bp)
AcroCR (MT945838 - MT945873)	AcroCR-F ^a : GCCCCTCAAGAGGGTTTCTA AcroCR-R ^a : CTAGACAGGGCCAAGGAGAAG	Ta: 55° 55 cycles	Same as for PCR amplification	1265 – 1352
PMCA (MT945609 - MT945656)	PMCA-F ^b : AAGGAATTGGTGGCTTTCTCCT PMCA-R ^b : CACAGACGACCATCTTTCCA	Ta: 53° 50 cycles	PMCA-Fint ^b : GAATTGGTGGCTTTCTCCTGAG PMCA-Rint ^b : CGACCATCTTTCCACTACCTTC	545
FZD (MT945657 - MT945718)	5491-F ^b : TATGGCTGCGACAATTTGGT 5491-R ^b : GCTAGCGTTTCGAGTTCAC FZD-F ^b : CCTTGAGTTGGTTCCTTGCT FZD-R ^b : CGCCTAGACAGCAGCTAAAA	Ta: 55° 50 cycles	5491-Fint ^b : CCTTGAGTTGGTTCCTTGCT 5491-Rint ^b : TCGAGTTCACCGTTCTTCT	639
TDH (MT945719 - MT945777)	TDH-F ^b : TTTTTCTTTCACCTTTTGGCTGT TDH-R ^b : ATCTCTGCTGCAATCCCAAT	Ta: 53° 50 cycles	Same as for PCR amplification ^c	994 – 1006 ^d
DOPR (MT945778 - MT945837)	DOPR-F ^b : AGGGTCAGGTTTTTGGGAAT DOPR-R ^b : GAGTTTTGACCGTCAGTTGG	Ta: 53° 50 cycles	Same as for PCR amplification ^c	736 – 744
ASNA (MT945874 - MT945940)	ASNA-F ^b : CTGTGTGCTGGCGAAAAA ASNA-R ^b : GAAAGGCCCTCTATTTTCA	Ta: 53° 50 cycles	Same as for PCR amplification ^c	747 – 760
				748 – 763

^a Primers designed and tested in-house.

^b Primers from previous studies (Ladner and Palumbi 2012).

^c Samples that proved difficult to amplify were re-amplified using M13-tailed PCR primers then sequenced using M13 primers M13F (TGTAACGACGGCCAGT) and M13R (CAGGAAACAGCTATGAC).

^d Product length was extended by assembling contigs using sequences obtained with previously reported primers (Ladner and Palumbi 2012), and sequences obtained using primers designed in-house.

General PCR conditions: start 1 sec 95°C; 1 min 95°C; [30 sec 95°C; 30 sec T° annealing (Ta); 2 min 72°C]x Number of cycles; 10 min 10°C. GenBank accession numbers (GenBank IDs) for the sequences obtained with each marker are also shown. Different internal primers (int) were used for sequencing in some cases.

TABLE S6. megaBLAST matches for the selected target capture loci and allelic exclusivity screening.

ID dataset	Accession numbers	Description	Code	FFRs gaps as 5th char.	FFRs masked gaps
Exon99029792	XM_029335609	<i>A. millepora</i> L-threonine 3-dehydrogenase	TDH	4	3
UCE111109	XM_015902484	<i>A. digitifera</i> dopamine receptor 2-like	DOPR	6	3
Exon2711	XM_029333081	<i>A. millepora</i> ATPase ASNA1 homolog	ASNA	7	4

The closest megaBLAST hit (accession numbers) is displayed for each of the loci derived from target enrichment sequencing along with a short description that was used to recode them accordingly throughout the text. The number of putative species or fields for recombination (FFRs) they delineated when used in the allele sharing-based approach based (both using gaps as a 5th character or masking them using HaplowebMaker; Spöri and Flot 2020) was used as proxy of their variability and resolution at species-level when compared to the primary species hypotheses (PSHs) derived from morphology.

TABLE S7. *Acropora* genome assemblies used for PCR primer design.

Species	Assembly version	Reference (source)
<i>A. digitifera</i> (Dana, 1846)	Adig_1.1	Shinzato et al. 2011 (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/10529)
<i>A. millepora</i> (Ehrenberg, 1834)	amil_sf_1.1	Ying et al. 2019 (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/2652)
<i>A. hyacinthus</i> (Dana, 1846)	Acropora_hyacinthus.discover_002	Liew et al. 2016, ReFuGe 2020 Consortium 2015 (http://ahya.reefgenomics.org/)
<i>A. palmata</i> (Lamarck, 1816)	Apalm_assembly_v1.0	Kitchen et al. 2019 (requested at: http://baumslab.org/research/data/)
<i>A. cervicornis</i> (Lamarck, 1816)	Acerv_assembly_v1.0	

Acropora genome assemblies used to map nuclear loci in order to design primers that maximized target product length for each region.

TABLE S8. Results of the haploweb allele sharing-based approach to delineate species.

Markers	Feature	Total	Morphospecies		
			<i>A. aff. hyacinthus</i>	<i>A. cf. bifurcata</i>	<i>A. cf. cytherea</i>
TDH	FFRs	3	1	1	1
	Exclusive alleles	20	8	8	4
	Shared alleles	0	0	0	0
DOPR	FFRs	6	4	1	1
	Exclusive alleles	23	14	4	5
	Shared alleles	0	0	0	0
ASNA	FFRs	9	6	1	2
	Exclusive alleles	35	16	10	9
	Shared alleles	0	0	0	0

Haplowebs delineate putative species according to the fields for recombination (FFRs), or common allele pools that can be identified. The absence of shared alleles between morphospecies supports the primary species hypotheses (PSHs) based on morphology, using the criterion of allelic exclusivity as indirect evidence for reproductive isolation.

TABLE S9. Testing alternative species models with the SNAPP coalescence-based approach.

Model	Model description	No. of species	MLE	BF	Rank
1	A single species of tabular <i>Acropora</i>	1	-1233.87	-366.13	3
2	Current taxonomy: <i>A. cytherea</i> and <i>A. hyacinthus</i> (lump <i>A. aff. hyacinthus</i> + <i>A. cf. bifurcata</i>)	2	-1050.80	---	2
3	Morphology + breeding trials + genetic clustering: <i>A. cf. cytherea</i> , <i>A. aff. hyacinthus</i> + <i>A. cf. bifurcata</i>	3	-880.96	339.68**	1

The most likely species models were ranked according to the Bayes factor delimitation (BFD) by calculating the average marginal likelihood estimates (MLE) of five SNAPP-BEAST runs to perform pairwise comparisons between the current taxonomy (model 2) and the alternative species models using Bayes factors (Kass and Raftery 1995):

$$BF = 2 * [MLE_x - MLE_1] \text{ (see Grummer et al. 2014; Herrera and Shank 2016)}$$

A positive BF value indicates support in favor of the alternative model, while a negative value indicates support of the current taxonomy (model 1) over the alternative one. BF values >10 (**) provide decisive support to distinguish between species models.

TABLE S10. Testing scenarios with different parameter prior distributions in Bayesian species delimitation using BPP.

ID	Scenario	Parameters	rjMCMC algorithm [parameters]	Most likely number of species [PP]	Best tree topology [PP]
1	Large ancestral population size and deep divergence of species	$\theta \sim \text{IG}(3, 0.2)$ mean = 0.1	0 [$\varepsilon=2$]	3 [1.0]	(B, (A, C)) [0.712165]
		$\tau_0 \sim \text{IG}(3, 0.2)$ mean = 0.1	1 [$\alpha= 2, m= 1$]	3 [1.0]	(B, (A, C)) [0.630295]
2	Small ancestral population size and shallow divergence of species	$\theta \sim \text{IG}(3, 0.002)$ mean = 0.001	0 [$\varepsilon=2$]	3 [1.0]	(A, (B, C)) [0.768815]
		$\tau_0 \sim \text{IG}(3, 0.002)$ mean = 0.001	1 [$\alpha= 2, m= 1$]	3 [1.0]	(A, (B, C)) [0.830950]
3	Large ancestral population size and shallow divergence of species ^a	$\theta \sim \text{IG}(3, 0.2)$ mean = 0.1	0 [$\varepsilon=2$]	3 [1.0]	(B, (A, C)) [0.435920]
		$\tau_0 \sim \text{IG}(3, 0.002)$ mean = 0.001	1 [$\alpha= 2, m= 1$]	3 [1.0]	(B, (A, C)) [0.471725]

^a Conservative combination of priors (large values for θ and small values for τ_0) that should favor models with a lower number of species (Leaché and Fujita 2010; McFadden et al. 2017).

Scenarios for testing the influence of three diffuse prior combinations (value 3 for the shape parameter), with inverse gamma distribution [$\text{IG}(\alpha, \beta)$] for population size (θ) and divergence time at the root of the species tree (τ_0) using Bayesian Phylogenetics and Phylogeography (BPP) (Yang 2015) for species delimitation. Posterior probabilities [PP] for the most likely number of species and the best tree topologies out of five runs are shown. Species in the topologies correspond to A) *A. aff. hyacinthus*, B) *A. cf. bifurcata*, C) *A. cf. cytherea*.

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